

Substituted Phenylhydrazines and their Derivatives

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Preparation of 2-chloro-5-bromo-, 2,5-dichloro-4-bromo-, 4-iodo-2-nitro-, and 4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-phenylhydrazines and their hydrazones with some carbonyl compounds are described.

In connection with some other work in this laboratory, a few phenylhydrazines and their condensation products with some carbonyl compounds were prepared by well known methods (Joshi and Deorha, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 14; 1951, 28, 34). Similar compounds are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Chloro-5-bromophenylhydrazine.—2-Chloro-5-bromoaniline (10.3 g.), suspended in HCl (conc., 50 c.c.), was diazotised by sodium nitrite (3.8 g.), dissolved in water (6 c.c.), at about 0°. The reaction product on treatment with a solution of stannous chloride (12 g.) in HCl (conc., 25 c.c.) separated as a crystalline precipitate of the hydrochloride of the corresponding base. It was washed with a saturated solution of sodium chloride and recrystallised from boiling HCl (dil.)

The base was obtained by adding an excess of NaOH solution to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride, extracting with ether, and then removing the solvent.

2,5-Dichloro-4-bromophenylhydrazine was similarly obtained from 2,5-dichloro-4-bromoaniline.

4-Iodo-2-nitrophenylhydrazine was obtained from 4-iodo-2-nitroaniline by the method adopted for the preparation of 2-iodo-4-nitrophenylhydrazine (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 14).

4,6-Dinitro-2-methylphenylhydrazine was prepared by the method already described (*ibid.*, 1951, 28, 34). Characteristics of the phenylhydrazines, prepared as above, are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Phenylhydrazine.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
2-Chloro-5-bromo-	69%	98°	Colorless	C ₆ H ₆ N ₂ ClBr	12.77	12.64
2,5-Dichloro-4-bromo-	70	107°	Do	C ₆ H ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br	11.11	10.93
4-Iodo-2-nitro-	75	123°	Red	C ₆ H ₄ O ₂ N ₂ I	14.96	15.05
4,6-Dinitro-2-methyl-	72	170°	Yellow	C ₇ H ₈ O ₂ N ₄	26.38	26.41

Characteristics of the phenylhydrazones, prepared by heating equimolecular quantities of the substituted phenylhydrazines and the carbonyl compounds in ethanol, are shown in Tables II and III.

TABLE II

Carbonyl compounds.	4-Iodo-2-nitro-2-methylphenylhydrazone.				4,6-Dinitro-2-methylphenylhydrazone.			
	M.P.	Colour	Formula	%Iodine. Found. Calc.	M.P.	Colour	Formula	%Nitrogen Found. Calc.
Formaldehyde	137°	Orange	C ₉ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃ I	43.52 43.64	140°	Yellow	C ₉ H ₉ O ₄ N ₄	25.12 25.0
Acetaldehyde	160°	Do	C ₉ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃ I	41.78 41.64	126°	Do	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₄	23.48 23.52
Benzaldehyde	215°	Red	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ I	34.49 34.60	196°	Vermillion	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₄	18.72 18.66
Salicylaldehyde	267°	Dark red	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ I	33.31 33.16	226°	Deep red	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₄	17.88 17.72
Vanillin	210°	Brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ I	30.82 30.75	240°	Red	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄	16.31 16.18
Cinnamic aldehyde	225°	Red	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ I	32.11 32.24	188°	Deep red	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₄	17.27 17.18
Anisaldehyde	195°	Brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ I	32.13 31.99	182°	Chocolate-brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄	16.78 16.96
Acetone	116°	Orange	C ₉ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃ I	40.14 39.81	128°	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄	22.28 22.22
Methyl ethyl ketone	105°	Orange-red	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ I	38.39 38.15	104°	Do	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄	21.12 21.05
Acetophenone	156°	Red	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ I	33.21 33.33	178°	Red	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₄	18.02 17.83
p-Methylacetophenone	172°	Do	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ I	32.31 32.15	203°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄	17.14 17.07

TABLE III

Carbonyl compounds.	2-Chloro-5-bromophenylhydrazone.				2,5-dichloro-4-bromophenylhydrazone.			
	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Calc.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
Benzaldehyde	112°	Colorless	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ ClBr	9.17 9.04	128°	Colorless	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br	8.24 8.13
Salicylaldehyde	150°	Do	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ON ₂ ClBr	8.48 8.60	172°	Do	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ Br	7.86 7.77
Vanillin	140°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClBr	7.92 7.87	156°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br	7.33 7.17
Cinnamic aldehyde	100°	Light yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClBr	8.12 8.34	185°	Light yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br	8.42 7.56
2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzaldehyde	228°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br	10.88 10.79	235°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃ Br	10.02 9.91